

Development of an Analytical Model for Bending Force Prediction during 3-Roller Conical Bending Process and Its Experimental Verification

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Abstract : Conical sections and shells made from metal plates are widely used in various industrial applications. 3-roller conical bending process is preferably used to produce such conical sections and shells. Bending mechanics involved in the process is complex and little work is done in this area. In the present paper an analytical model is developed to predict the bending force required during 3-roller conical bending process. To verify the developed model, conical bending experiments were performed. Analytical results and experimental results were compared. It is observed that the error in the prediction is $\pm 10\%$. Hence the developed model can be used to estimate the bending force during 3-roller bending process and can be useful to the designers for designing the 3-roller conical bending machine.

Keywords : roll bending, internal moment, external moment, analytical model, bending force, experimental verification

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